

MULTI-DISCIPLINARY DESIGN OPTIMIZATION OF SANDWICH CONSTRUCTIONS

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1 Introduction

Sandwich constructions have the major advantage of being very lightweight. In addition to that advantage, economic advantages as well as technical requirements are vital for the potential use of sandwich constructions in many engineering applications. The principal interest of the optimization of sandwich structures, compared to the optimization of metal structures, is to introduce the internal structure of the sandwich (the core) in the variables of the optimization problem. It is thus important to provide a method to optimize the sandwich constructions in multi-disciplinary way, and that already in the stage of materials selection. Multi-disciplinary design optimization looks to find solutions for an engineering problem where several criteria are interdependently coupled. The solutions of the simultaneous problem are better to the solutions found by optimizing each criterion sequentially, since it can exploit the interactions and trades between the criteria, hence the multicriteria optimization is privileged. Some works has already been developed in this way which either use only the numerical approach (e.g. Hudson: Multiple objective optimization of composite sandwich structures for rail vehicle floor panels (2009)) or only material selection charts (e.g. Pflug: Sandwich material selection charts (2006)), and these works consider only two criteria. The aim of the research at IKT is to find an approach for multicriteria optimization of sandwiches, which would be valid for a variable number of criteria, by using numerical approach coupled with materials selection charts.

2 Appropriate research method

For multicriteria optimization of sandwiches, methods capable of handling a large number of variables (some discrete and some others continuous) and objectives, often non-differentiable must be identified. There are generally two main families of methods of research: deterministic and stochastic. The stochastic methods are characterized by a process of random creation of the points in space's research and a method for ensuring convergence of the algorithm. These methods are used to find an approximate solution to the global optimum in the case of strongly multimodal problems with a lot of variables. They are generally so-called direct methods, who making it possible to work without any derivation and analytical formulation of objective functions. They are consequently adapted to combinatorial problems such as non-linear problems, defined on continuous spaces as well as discrete or mixed, with or without constraints [1]. It is thus the stochastic methods that are chosen for the multicriteria optimization of sandwich constructions. Among the various stochastic methods, genetic algorithms (GA) have been proposed by many authors to solve the problem of multicriteria optimization. The originality and the fundamental interest of AG are in their ability to manipulate a population and to exploit the information exchanges between solutions, what are not possible for other stochastic methods [2].

3 Operating mode of GA (general and in this case)

A genetic Algorithm is a population-based iteration scheme, which examines parallel multiple parameters sets in each iteration step. A benchmark principle is adopted on the sets in terms of one or

more objective functions to accomplish an optimal solution by truncation of the algorithm. After an initial phase at the beginning of the optimisation a specific search over multiple generations is enforced. In every generation the objective function is evaluated for all sets, the highest fitness is assigned to the best solutions. Executing evolutionary operators like recombination and mutation on fitness-based selected individuals leads to new parameter sets for the next generation. This process ideally leads to even better solutions [2]. The Figure below shows the basic scheme of genetic algorithm, as conceived by Holland in 1975.

Fig. 1. Basic scheme of a GA [3]

Several popular approaches have been used by different researchers for multicriteria optimization, each one having its merits as demerits.

4 Benchmark case study

5 Applications of the genetic algorithm to the case study

6 Comparison with the calculated results

References

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